

SMART DRAW AR: USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND AR TECHNOLOGIES IN ARCHITECTURE AND CONSTRUCTION EDUCATION**Sheraliyev Sanjarbek Karimberdiyevich**Teacher at the National Pedagogical University of
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Abstract: This article analyzes the importance of applying modern digital technologies in architectural and construction education. In particular, the capabilities, operating principles, and role of the innovative platform "Smart Draw AR" in increasing educational efficiency will be highlighted. The platform is based on artificial intelligence (AI), augmented reality (AR), and 3D modeling technologies, serving the interactive study of technical drawings. The article provides extensive coverage of the project's concept, practical significance, technical capabilities, and expected results.

Keywords: AR technology, artificial intelligence, 3D modeling, engineering graphics, drafting, architecture, construction education, interactive platform, innovative education.

In today's era of globalization and digital transformation, the implementation of modern technologies into the education system is considered one of the pressing issues. In particular, the application of innovative technologies in the fields of architecture and construction plays an important role in improving the quality of the educational process.

In teaching traditional drawing and engineering graphics, students often face difficulties in visualizing complex objects due to insufficient development of their spatial thinking. Perceiving 2D drawings in 3D form, spatial analysis of technical details, and visualizing real structures pose problems for many students.

Therefore, the development of innovative platforms based on the use of modern AR (Augmented Reality), AI (Artificial Intelligence) and 3D technologies is one of the important tasks of today.

"Smart Draw AR" is an innovative digital platform designed for teaching architecture and engineering graphics, combining artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and 3D modeling technologies.

Using this platform, students can: studies technical drawings in 3D format, visualizes virtual objects in a real environment using AR technology, identifies errors in drawings using

AI, participates in interactive classes via mobile devices, conducts practical classes in virtual laboratories.

The primary objective of the platform is to enhance educational efficiency by teaching engineering graphics and architecture based on modern pedagogical technologies.

The platform operates based on several technological stages.

At the first stage, the student uploads a technical drawing or project file to the system. At the next stage, the AI module automatically analyzes the drawing and identifies geometric errors, projection defects, and dimensional inaccuracies.

Then, using AR technology, a 3D model is created based on the drawing. The student will be able to see this model in a real environment using a mobile phone or tablet camera.

This approach allows the student to: develops spatial thinking, forms technical thinking, reinforces practical skills, improves self-education skills.

A number of modern software tools are used in the project development.

AutoCAD-Serves for creating technical drawings and preparing projects.

AUTOCAD
Texnik chizmalar yaratish va loyihalarni tayyorlash uchun xizmat qiladi.

ANIQ CHIZMALAR 3D MODELASHTIRISH TIZ VA SAMARALI LOYIHALARNI TAYYORLASH CHOP ETISH VA EXPORT

AUTOCAD NIMA?
Autocad - bu Autodesk kompaniyasining kuchli va korp funksiyali dasturi bo'lib, 2D texnik chizmalar va 3D modelar yaratish, loyihalash, tahrirlash va hujjatlash uchun ishlatiladi.

QO'LLANISH SOHALARI

- ARXITEKTURA
- QURILISH
- MUHANDISLIK
- MASHINASOZLIK

- Archi va sifali texnik chizmalar
- Vazir va samarali tajayb
- Loyihalash jarayonini soddalashtiradi
- Boshqa dasturlar bilan integratsiya

SketchUp is used in 3D modeling of architectural objects.

SketchUp
ARXITEKTURA OBYEKTLARINI 3D MODELASHTIRISHDA QO'LLANILADI

SketchUp - arxitektura, qurilish, interyer va landschaft dizayni uchun kuchli va oson 3D modelashtirish dasturi.

- 3D MOGELLASHTIRISH**
Binolar, inshootlar va turli arxitektura obyektlarini 3D ko'rinishda yaratish.
- O'SON VA QULAY**
Oddiy interfeys va qulay vositalar yordamida tezkor modelashtirish.
- ANIQ VA DETALLASHTIRILGAN**
Aniq o'lchamlar, materiallar va detallarga e'tibor qaratish imkoniyati.
- LOYIHALASH VA TAQDIMOT**
Chizmalar, kesimlar, fasadlar va taqdimot uchun yuqori sifati ko'rsatkichlar.
- BOSHQA DASTURLAR BILAN INTEGRATSIYA**
Autocad, Lumion, Enscape, V-Ray va boshqa dasturlar bilan mos ishlaydi.

TEKNOF MODELASHTIRISH ANIQ O'LCHAMLAR MATERIALLAR VA TEXTURALAR CHIZMALAR VA DOKUMENTATSIYA YUQORI SIFATLI VIZUALIZATSIYA

QO'LLANISH SOHALARI

- ARXITEKTURA LOYIHALASH
- QURILISH LOYIHALARI
- INTERYER DIZAYN
- LANDSHAFT DIZAYN
- MEBEL LOYIHALASH
- URBANISTIKA

Blender allows you to create 3D animations and virtual objects.

Unity serves as the primary platform for creating 3D-AR systems.

Python and TensorFlow are used to develop artificial intelligence modules.

python + TensorFlow
SUN'YI INTELLEKT MODULLARINI ISHLAB CHIQUISH UCHUN ASOSIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR

PYTHON

- Sodda va oson Sintaksisi sodda va o'rganish oson.
- Kuchli kutubxonalar NumPy, Pandas, OpenCV, Scikit-learn va boshqalar.
- Tez ishlab chiqish AI modullarini tez va samarali yaratish imkonini beradi.
- Kross-platforma Windows, Linux, macOS va boshqa platformalarda ishlaydi.

SUN'YI INTELLEKT ISHLASH JARAYONI

MALUMOTLARNI TOPLASH → MALUMOTLARNI QAYTA ISHLASH → MODELNI YARATISH → O'QITISH (TRAINING) → BAHLASH VA FOYDALANISH

TENSORFLOW

- Kuchli AI platformasi** ML va DL modullarini yaratish va o'qitish uchun ochiq manbali platforma.
- Moalshuvchanlik** Tadqiqot, prototiplash va ishlab chiqarish uchun mos.
- Yuqori samaradorlik** GPU/TPU qo'llab-quvvatlashi orqali katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlar ustida ishlaydi.
- Ishlab chiqarishga tayyor** Modern turl platformalarga joylash (Deploy) imkonini beradi.

QO'LLANILADIGAN KUTUBXONALAR

NumPy, Pandas, OpenCV, Keras

QO'LLANISH SOHALARI

Kompyuter ko'rish (Image Detection, Image Classification), NLP (Matn sarhif, Chatbotlar), Prognozlash (Time Series, Regression), Intellectual tizimlar va avtomatlashtirish

MODEL ISHLASH MISOLI

Kirish ma'lumoti: 3 → Model → Baholalar: 3 (Amplik: 98.6%)

AFZALLIKLARI

- ✓ Ochiq manbali va bepul
- ✓ Katta hajmli yordam
- ✓ Ko'p platforma qo'llab-quvvatlash
- ✓ Tez va samarali ishlash
- ✓ Ilmiy tadqiqotlar va amaliy loyihalar uchun ideal

Moodle will be integrated as a distance learning and assessment system.

moodle
MASOFAYIY TA'LIM VA BAHLASH TIZIMI

Moodle – ochiq kodli (open source) o'quv platformasi bo'lib, masofaviy ta'lim jarayonini boshqarish, o'quv materialini tarqatish, topshiriqlarni qabul qilish va baholash tizimi sifatida integratsiya qilinadi.

ASOSIY IMKONIYATLAR

- Masofaviy o'qish va erish
- Topshiriqlar va testlar
- Baholash va natijalarni tahlil qilish
- Mobil va funktsion
- Xavfsiz va shaxsiylik

TIZIM IMKONIYATLARI

- KIRIS BOSHQARUVI** Funksion, qat'iyat, baholash va baholash.
- FOYDALANUVCHILAR** O'qituvchi, talabalar va mahalliy talabalar boshqaruvi.
- O'QUV MATERIALLARI** Fayllar, formatlar (SCORM, xP) va boshqa resurslarni yuklash.
- TOPSHIRIQLAR** Topshiriqlar berish, qabul qilish va baholash.
- TEST VA SO'ROVHOMALAR** Onlayn testlar, so'rovnomalar va viktorinalar yaratish.
- BAHOLASH TIZIMI** Baholarni avtomatik yoki qo'l bilan baholash va tahlil qilish.
- FORUMLAR VA CHAT** Forumlar, chat va sahifa lar orqali muloqot qilish.
- KABARHOMALAR** E-mail va bildirimlar orqali xabarlar berish.

MOBILE ILOVA

Moodle mobil ilova orqali talabalar joyida ta'lim olish va baholash imkonini beradi.

INTEGRATSIYA IMKONIYATLARI

- LMS FLUGHLARI** Barcha platformalar bilan integratsiya.
- UCHUNDE YOMON XIZMATLARI** Zoom, Google Drive, Microsoft Teams va boshqa mahalliy ilmlar integratsiya.
- API VA WEB XIZMATLAR** Barcha mahalliy ilmlar bilan integratsiya.
- XAVFSIZLIK** Ma'lumotlar mahalliy va bulutli mahalliy ilmlar bilan integratsiya.

MOODLE AFZALLIKLARI

- ✓ Ochiq kodli va bepul
- ✓ Foydalanuvchi qo'llab-quvvatlash
- ✓ Moalshuvchanlik va kengaytirilgan
- ✓ Tez qo'llaniladigan ilovalar
- ✓ Kuchli kutubxonalar
- ✓ Katta hajmli yordam

The main innovative features of the "Smart Draw AR" project are:

1. An automated AI-powered assessment system.
2. Interactive laboratories based on AR.

3. Automatically convert 2D drawings to 3D view.
4. Ability to work on mobile and web platforms.
5. An innovative educational platform for engineering graphics in Uzbek.

This platform serves to modernize the educational process and develop the creative and technical potential of students.

The project can be effectively used in the following educational institutions: higher educational institutions, technical schools, vocational schools, distance learning platforms.

Also, with the help of the platform: paper costs will decrease, material resources are saved through virtual laboratories, the visual quality of education will improve, distance learning opportunities will expand.

As a result of this project: an interactive AR platform will be created, an automated verification system using AI will be implemented, virtual laboratories will be developed, a modern digital educational environment is being formed, the methodology for teaching engineering graphics will be improved.

In conclusion, the "Smart Draw AR" project is a modern digital platform aimed at implementing innovative pedagogical technologies in architectural and construction education. This platform will significantly improve the quality of teaching technical disciplines by integrating artificial intelligence, augmented reality, and 3D modeling technologies into a single system.

Nowadays, when teaching engineering graphics, drafting, and architecture, students often face difficulties in the spatial representation of complex technical drawings. The "Smart Draw AR" platform serves to eliminate these problems. With the help of the platform, students will be able to view simple 2D drawings in 3D mode in real time, analyze virtual objects in a real environment using AR technology, and automatically detect their mistakes using artificial intelligence.

Another important aspect of the project is that it develops interactivity and independent learning skills, which are one of the main requirements of modern education. Students will be able to independently complete practical exercises through virtual laboratories, mobile applications, and interactive assignments. This not only increases the efficiency of the educational process but also serves to develop students' creativity and technical thinking.

The practical significance of this platform lies in the fact that it can be effectively used in higher educational institutions, technical schools, construction colleges, and general education

schools. The project will also expand the possibilities of distance learning, reduce paper and laboratory costs, and contribute to the formation of a digital educational environment.

In the future, by further improving the "Smart Draw AR" platform, it is possible to create virtual laboratories in the field of construction and architecture, automatic project analysis using AI, and interactive educational systems that meet international standards.

Thus, the "Smart Draw AR" project is of great importance not only as an innovative educational product but also as a promising technological solution for the digitalization of architectural and construction education.

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